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Review Article

**HERBOSOMES - A NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY CARRIER
FOR ENHANCED BIOAVAILABILITY OF HERBAL
EXTRACTS****V. Anusha^{1*}, R. Kusuma², B. Swathi³, N. Rajani⁴, Aruna Kuthani⁵**^{1, 2, 3, 4, 5} Department of Pharmaceutics, Bojjam Narasimhulu Pharmacy College for women,
Hyderabad, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

Herbal treatments also consistently and significantly contribute to the development of human health in comparison with allopathic treatments. From ancient times, herbal preparations were considered as the most essential type of medicine in all the civilizations. The numerous plant extracts have exhibited an extensive range of biological activity, like immunomodulator activity, hepatoprotective activity, antilipidemic action, etc. Herbal extracts obtained from plants demonstrate great in vitro bioactivity and exhibits low in vivo action in animal models. The foremost explanations for this behavior is that the bioactive components have the composition that cannot be permeated by simple passive diffusion, and most of the phytoconstituents are polar water soluble compounds, which results in their poor lipid solubility. This issue can be resolved by formulation of herbosomes which are the novel lipid based drug delivery system which delivers the herbal extract at the targeted site of activity with improved absorption, bioavailability and efficacy. They assists to overcome the challenges of bioavailability issues by forming herbosome complex. They include complex comprising herbal natural extract with suitable phospholipids like phosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylserine, etc. This advanced technique has been developing as an approach to enhance the medicinal potential of plant based extracts.

Key words: Herbosomes, phospholipids, bioavailability, phytomedicines, phytoconstituents

Corresponding author:**V Anusha,**Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics,
Bojjam Narasimhulu Pharmacy College for women
Hyderabad, Telangana, India.E-mail: anuv1709@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION:

The herbs are usually considered as the oldest remedies which were used as a safer and more effective alternatives to the existing conventional contemporary synthetic medications which could exhibit unwanted side effects. The plant derived herbal pharmaceuticals have gained popularity and availability to the medical markets across the whole world. From the ancient time plant based phytomedicines were utilized for the treatment of various illnesses. Numerous plant material have demonstrated a wide variety of biological activity such as hepato protective activity, anti lipidemic activity, anticancer activity, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anticancer. Hypoglycemic activity etc. However many phytomedicines are inadequate in their effectiveness since they are poorly absorbed when administered by oral route [1].

In the term Herbosomes, the word "Herbo" is reflected as plant and "some" indicates cell like structure. The research conducted on plants describes that maximum number of compounds of plant origin are polar in nature or water soluble molecules. In this scenario the large size polar molecules cannot cross easily the cellular lipid structure barrier, the examples includes polar flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, etc. This type of molecules cannot be absorbed by normal transport mechanisms like passive diffusion because of their poor lipid solubility and lower lipid concentration levels, which limits their capacity to pass through the lipid rich biological barrier membrane further leads to poor bioavailability of the therapeutically active constituents.

These novel carrier systems of Herbosomes have established to be extremely efficient in protection of pharmaceutically, therapeutically active herbal extracts against gastrointestinal conditions including the gastric secretions and gut bacteria. The herbosomes of various herbal extracts like ginseng, milk thistle, grape seed, green tea, etc are available in the market. Herbosomes are lipid based drug

delivery system that includes phospholipids along with active constituents of herbal extracts, improving the bioavailability of water-soluble phytomedicines. They are considered as lipid-compatible phospholipid complexes which includes phospholipids bound with plant extracts. It is considered as a vesicular novel drug delivery system which encompasses lipid and phytoconstituents [2-3]. These Herbosomes elevates the bioavailability of the phytoconstituents materials by improving their absorption.

Herbosomes are beneficial in delivering the herbal drug component at a required rate, delivering to necessary site of action, which diminishes the unwanted adverse effects along with enhancement of the bioavailability of medication.

Herbosomes structure

In herbosomes the term "herbo" means the bioactive therapeutic component of the herbosome carrier system which is obtained from plants. These Herbosome complex carriers are supported to be compatible with hydrophilic and lipophilic media. In terms of their chemical nature they bear a resemblance to cell membranes structure and act as a means for delivering herbal constituents. Phospholipids and polyphenols interact properly in nonpolar solvents, which are used in the herbosomes preparation [4]. The hydrogen bonds as primary interaction between the polar groups which are designated by phosphate groups and bioactive material that are present in phytosomal structures of plant constituents, provide the origin for production of Herbosomes. It was specified that the production of H-bonds among the phosphate group of phosphatidylcholines and hydroxyl part of the catechin was the primary interaction happening in catechin-loaded Herbosomes preparation [5]. Upon exposure to water, Herbosomes usually exhibit a structure similarity as liposomes. The structure of herbosome and its difference from liposome is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Herbosome and liposome comparison

Mechanism involved in formation of herbosomes

Herbosomes are produced in an aprotic solvent with the reaction of phospholipids such as soy phosphatidylcholine with standard extract or polyphenolic constituent's compounds such as simple flavonoids. Phosphatidylcholine is observed to be a bifunctional compound with a lipophilic phosphatidyl moiety and a hydrophilic choline moiety. In the phosphatidylcholine specifically the choline head binds to these compounds, whereas lipid soluble phosphatidyl portion encompassing the body and tail will then envelope the choline bound material. This interaction leads to, the phytomolecules forming a lipid-soluble molecular complex with phospholipids which is termed as phyto-phospholipid complex [6]. Plant derived phytomolecules are chemically bound to polar choline head groups of phospholipids, as established by spectroscopic techniques. The chemical analysis methods indicated that herbosome is characteristically a flavonoid molecule connected to at least one molecule of phosphatidylcholine.

Advantages of herbosomes

- They pass rapidly through the cell membrane barrier and enters the cell.
- They assist in improving the bioavailability of polar phytoconstituents compounds by augmenting their absorption through various routes including nasal, topical, etc.
- They protect the plant extract and safeguards it from gastrointestinal secretions and gut wall bacteria [7].
- They Herbosomes support the delivery of drug to the intended tissue and organ by proper targeted delivery of medications.
- The dose required for the therapeutically active phytochemical constituents can be reduced because maximum absorption, is observed with improved bioavailability.
- The phosphatidylcholine molecule interacts chemically with the plant derived phytoconstituents, representing the high stability of Herbosomes [8].
- These preparations are frequently used in cosmetics which assist in increasing the transdermal absorption of phytoconstituents due to enhanced skin penetration with high lipid profile.
- They are biodegradable in nature. They are considered as suitable for administration of phytoconstituents because they upsurge the impact of herbal ingredients by improving absorption, biological activity, along with targeted delivery to the required location.
- In cosmetic skincare products, herbosomes are beneficial when compared to other vesicular delivery system like liposomes [8].
- Phosphatidylcholine, which is utilized in the preparation of Herbosomes acts as a

hepatoprotective, it has a synergistic influence when united with hepatoprotective substances.

- They can be prepared into a powerful semisolid dosage form because of their low water solubility [8].

Disadvantages of herbosomes

- The phytoconstituent compounds in herbosomes are rapidly removed from body.
- They usually exhibit a short half-life which impacts their activity [9].
- The phospholipids utilized in the formulation of herbosomes undergo hydrolysis, leakage, stability problems like oxidation, etc.
- The cost of production is high, and there might be chances of allergic responses to the constituents of the herbosomes [9].

Applications of herbosomes

- They are used in treatment of liver conditions, hepatitis, with alcoholic hepatic steatosis, drug-induced liver damage conditions.
- They exhibit anti-inflammatory actions and are united into pharmaceutical and also cosmetic preparations [10].
- Acute and chronic liver diseases can be treated utilizing herbosomes [10]
- They also used in the treatments as immunomodulators, anti-wrinkle representatives, and anti-aging agents, etc.
- They are used as anticancer agents and antioxidant, example, grape seed extract formulation.
- Herbosomes are used in the treatment of hyperlipidemia and also in management of hypertension [10].

Properties of Herbosomes

1) Physicochemical properties

They are the combination of a natural plant based product and naturally derived phospholipids, such as soy phospholipids. A complex which is produced by this includes a reaction where amounts of phospholipids and substrate are reacted in a suitable solvent. It has been established that there is formation of hydrogen bonds between polar heads of phospholipids that is with phosphate and ammonium groups and the polar functionalities of the substrate to be the main phospholipids substrate interaction based on the specific spectroscopic data. In presence of water, herbosomes exhibit micellar shape and produce liposomal structure. While the active functional ingredient in liposomes is dissolved in internal pocket or if it floats in the layer membrane, the constituents in Herbosome is bound

to the polar heads of phospholipids and becomes a structural component of membrane [11].

2) Biological properties: These are more progressive products than usual herbal extracts and are better effectively absorbed and accordingly offer improved effects. Pharmacokinetic studies or pharmacodynamics investigations on experimental animals and humans have demonstrated that the herbosomes have greater bioavailability than non complexed botanical plant derivatives [11]

Functions of Phospholipid in formulation of herbosomes

Phospholipids are acquired from natural and synthetic sources. They are extensively found in plants, animals, and the chief sources includes vegetable oils, soya bean, sunflower seed, flaxseed, cotton and animal tissues like egg yolk, bovine brain, etc. The studies indicates that phospholipids are considered as one of the most plentifully present lipid fractions in the natural biological membranes and could form bilayers and acts as amphipathic molecules [12]. Phospholipids are absorbed to abundant extent after oral administration and reaches the peak plasma concentration within a duration of 6 hours. FDA and German Cancer Research Centre, Heidelberg specified that Soy phosphatidylcholine has no carcinogenicity and no risk in formation of tumours. Furthermore, it is assumed to have diverse advanced useful properties like hepatoprotective activity, nutritional supplement for supporting the brain health, along with role in membrane fluidity, outstanding emulsifying activity, precursor for acetylcholine, The examples of few phospholipids used are presented in table 1.

S. No	Natural phospholipids	Synthetic Phospholipids
1.	Phosphatidylcholine (PC)	Dioleoyl Phosphatidylcholine (DOPC)
2.	Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)	Dioleoyl phosphatidyl ethanolamine (DOPE)
3.	Phosphatidylserine (PS)	Distearoyl phosphatidyl choline (DSPC)
4.	Phosphatidylinositol (PI)	Distearoyl phosphatidyl ethanolamine (DSPE)

2) Plant derived Extract: The water-soluble phytoconstituents like flavonoids, polyphenols, etc.

3) Solvent: The following solvents are used

a) Aprotic Solvent: They are used to enable the reaction between phytoconstituents and phospholipids. Eg: Dioxane, acetone, methylene chloride [13].

b) Non-solvent: n-hexane used as non- solvent for precipitating herbosomes.

c) Alcohol: Methanol and ethanol are used in formulation of herbosomes

d) Other solvents: The other solvents utilized includes tetrahydrofuran, dichloromethane.

4) Buffering agent: Saline phosphate buffer (pH 6.5), Tris buffer with pH 6.5 are used as a hydrating

Methods of preparation

decreasing serum cholesterol levels, improving the sensitivity of taste and smell, nourishment of skin, etc [12].

Phospholipid acts as a main moiety in composition of cellular and subcellular membrane. The human body utilizes phospholipid as emulsifiers and improves the absorption of fat-soluble materials. Additionally, it also acts as surface active agent in pleura and alveoli of the lung, joints, pericardium, etc. They could be extracted from egg yolk or from soybeans through mechanical or by chemical methods with the assistance of hexane. Phosphatidylcholine is composed of two main groups the lipophilic, phosphatidyl group, and the polar choline group. The choline moiety increases memory function and assistances muscle control. This choline portion binds to herbal extract while this phosphatidyl group shields and covers the phytoconstituents like form of cell which additionally safeguards the active constituent from damage due to the digestive juices. This complex formation improves the bioavailability of the active constituent, along with prolonged duration of activity [12].

Formulation of Herbosomes

Ingredients used in formulation of herbosomes

The following ingredients are utilized in the preparation of herbosomes formulations

1) Phospholipids: The examples include Soy phosphatidylcholine, Egg phosphatidylcholine, Dipalmitoyl phosphatidylcholine, Distearoyl phosphatidylcholine as a vesicle forming element [13].

The following techniques are usually employed in the preparation of herbosomes

1) Rotary evaporation technique

2) Solvent evaporation technique

3) Ether injection technique

4) Gas anti-solvent technique

5) Solution enhanced dispersion by supercritical fluids (SEDS)

6) Lyophilization technique

These are the advanced complexes which are formed by reacting 3 to 2 moles, but more precisely though one mole of natural or with synthetic phospholipids, like phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylserine, using one mole of plant based components, which can be in their pure form or as part of the natural mixture, by means of aprotic solvents like dioxane

or acetone. As the complex is formed, it can be isolated by precipitation technique using a non-solvent, like aliphatic hydrocarbons, or by the methods like lyophilization, spray drying [14]. The characteristic molar ratio between phospholipid and active plant compound frequently ranges from 0.5 to 2.0, with a 1:1 ratio of phospholipids to flavonoids being the usually chosen for optimum complex formation.

1) Rotary evaporation technique

It involves dissolving accurately weighed quantity of plant material along with phospholipid in adequate quantity of tetrahydrofuran within a round-bottom rotary flask followed by stirring for 3 hours at a temperature not more than 40°C. Then the solvent has been evaporated to produce a thin film. Then N-hexane was added to film followed by continuous stirring of mixture by means of a magnetic stirrer, which further leads to formation of precipitate. This preparation can be collected and transferred into an amber colored glass bottle and further stored at room temperature [15].

2) Solvent Evaporation Method

The measured amount of herbal material along with phospholipids are added to round bottom flask of 100 ml followed by reflux with around 20 ml of acetone at temperature of 50–60°C for duration of 2 hours. The resulting mixture was then concentrated to produce a final volume of 5 ml–10 ml, which allows the formation of precipitate. It was filtered, collected followed by drying, and further stored in an amber colored glass bottle at normal room temperature [15].

3) Ether injection technique

This method includes the dissolving of drug and lipid complex in a suitable organic solvent. Then the solution progressively injected into heated aqueous medium, this further leads to formation of the vesicles. They can produce vesicles with various structures like round, cylindrical, disc, hexagonal or cubic shapes [15].

4) Gas anti-solvent technique

It includes addition of weighed quantity of plant herbal extract and also measure quantity of phospholipid in a 100 ml round-bottom flask followed by reflux with dichloromethane with volume of 20 ml at temperature not more than 60°C for duration of 2 hours. After completing the reflux the resulting mixture was then concentrated to produce a final volume of 5 ml–10 ml. Then, hexane with a quantity of 20 ml was gradually added to the mixture with continuous stirring, this produces a precipitate [16]. This produced precipitate was then filtered, collected and was stored in a suitable desiccator overnight for complete drying. After drying the precipitate was pulverized using mortar and pestle then passed through sieve number #100 mesh to achieve a fine powder. This final powdered complex can be stored in amber colored glass bottle at room temperature by transferring into it.

5) Solution enhanced dispersion by supercritical fluids (SEDS)

This technique includes continuous addition of liquid solvent solution and supercritical antisolvent carbon dioxide into the suitable precipitation unit. A nozzle with 0.1 mm diameter is utilized to send carbon dioxide gas into a mixture containing mixture of phospholipids and herbal plant material along with solvent. The ideal experimental conditions are 35 °C, 10 mPa pressure [16].

6) Lyophilization technique:

The method involves dissolving natural or synthetic phospholipid and plant based phytoconstituent in different solvents and to continue the process the solution comprising phytoconstituent is added with solution encompassing phospholipid which is followed by continuous stirring until complex is formed. The complex which is produced is further isolated by Lyophilization technique [16].

Evaluation and characterization of Herbosomes

1. Visualization: To visualize herbosomes Transmission electron microscopy-TEM, scanning electron microscopy - SEM can be used [17].
2. Entrapment efficiency: To estimate the entrapment of medication in herbosomes preparation ultracentrifugation method can be utilized [17].
3. Vesicle size and zeta potential: The particle size along with Zeta potential could be determined using Dynamic Light Scattering - DLS utilizing a computerized system and photon correlation spectroscopy- PCS [18].
4. Surface tension determination: The surface tension of drug in a solution will be assessed by utilizing Du Nouy ring tensiometer method [18].
5. Transition temperature: A Differential scanning Calorimetry technique - DSC will assist in analyzing the transition temperature of vesicular systems [19].
6. Vesicle stability: The stability of produced vesicles can be estimated by observing changes in its size and structure with course of time. This mean size is measured utilizing DLS while the structural changes are measured with the assistance of TEM technique [19].
7. Drug content: The drug content can be analyzed by high performance liquid chromatographic approach or by utilizing any suitable spectroscopic technique to quantify the quantity of the drug [20]. The other studies are also considered in characterization of herbosomes which includes in-vitro and in-vivo release studies, spectroscopic evaluation using FTIR, NMR studies, etc [20].

CONCLUSION:

The plant derived components like exhibit huge therapeutic potential but their usage in disease treatment has been challenging. These challenges are observed because the herbal based materials are

unable to pass through the barrier of lipid layers due to their polar nature. In this scenario the novel formulation herbosomes acts as a means to overcome the above discussed problems by enhancing the movement of material through lipid barriers with improved bioavailability. They act as connection between conventional formulations and novel drug delivery formulations. The herbal extracts are well absorbed with improved efficiency through the herbosomes in comparison with traditional herbal preparations. They offer broad range of applications in the field of cosmetic sector. They assist in maintaining higher concentrations of the active materials to reach the target organ and tissues like brain, heart, liver, kidneys, etc at low or same doses. Numerous phytoconstituents were delivered utilizing this method, exhibiting remarkable therapeutic potential in human and animal studies. They direct a promising future in field of formulation development for delivery of hydrophilic polar plant based compounds, with a proper selection and screening these herbosomes can be modified for different therapeutic purposes, predominantly as a nutraceuticals for prevention of diseases and maintenance of good health.

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